

Choice of Hernioplasty Method in Patients with Inguinal Hernias

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Annotation: Purpose of the study – to elaborate an algorithm for the choice of hernioplasty method in patients with inguinal hernias on the basis of analysis of the pathological changes, which have appeared as a result of the hernia formation, and of the features observed in anatomic structure of the inguinal canal. During the period of 2016 to 2022, 306 patients with inguinal hernias, aged 16 to 82 years, were operated on at Bukhara regional multidisciplinary medical center. Mostly, they were male patients – 260 (85%). Primary inguinal hernias were diagnosed in 260 (85%), recurrent hernias in 46 (15%) patients. Used in the study was the inguinal hernia classification by Gilbert. According to this classification and with an account for the inguinal interspace height and a degree of atrophic changes in muscle-aponeurotic structures of the inguinal canal, we worked out the following algorithm for the choice of hernioplasty method. In case of hernias of types I, II, III, IV and V with the preserved posterior wall of the inguinal canal, with the lowered inguinal interspace (up to 2 cm) and lacking atrophy in muscle-aponeurotic structures of the inguinal canal, either autoplasty of the posterior wall of the inguinal canal or transabdominal preperitoneal laparoscopic hernioplasty is indicated; alloplasty by Liechtenstein method is possible at patient's will. In case of hernia types VI and VIII with the lowered inguinal interspace and lacking atrophy in muscle-aponeurotic structures of the inguinal canal, either alloplasty of the posterior wall of the inguinal canal by Liechtenstein method or PHS is indicated. For hernia types III, IV, V, VI, VII and VIII with the higher inguinal interspace (3 to 5 cm) and existent atrophy in muscle-aponeurotic structures of the inguinal canal, either allohernioplasty by Reeves method or preperitoneal allohernioplasty of inguinal and femoral hernias is indicated. Using the algorithm proposed for the choice of hernioplasty method, 21 (6.8%) autoplasmic and 285 (93.2 %) alloplasmic operations were performed at our Clinic. During the postoperative period, infiltrate in the wound area and serous inflammation were observed in 6 (2.1 %) patients, moderate edema of testicle in 3 (2.8%) and suppuration in 1 (0.3%) patients. Hernial recurrences occurred in 3 (1.05%) patients out of those 285 examined within 1 to 5 years. An improvement in the surgical treatment results in patients with inguinal hernias can be achieved by means of the individual choice of hernioplasty method with an account for pathological changes in the posterior wall of the inguinal canal and the inguinal interspace height, technically adequate performance of the operation itself, and the use of up-to-date mesh implants. The algorithm proposed for the choice of hernioplasty method allows for minimization of the recurrence rate of inguinal hernias. The present-day classifications of inguinal hernias do not give complete information about pathological changes in the inguinal canal and need to be supplemented.

Keywords: inguinal hernia, aloplasty, choice of operation method, prolene mesh.

INTRODUCTION

The results of surgical treatment of inguinal hernias indicate a significant progress in the treatment of this pathology, thanks to the introduction of alloplasty and laparoscopic operations. At the same time, the recurrence rate of inguinal hernia after alloplasty at primary hernioplasty is 0.5-1.5%, and at repeated hernioplasty 1.5-7% [1-4, 6-7]. Significantly worse results are observed with autografting, as the recurrence rate of inguinal hernia in primary hernioplasty is 5.7-10%, and in repeat hernioplasty 15-36% [1-4]. Improving the results of surgical treatment of this type of hernia can be achieved through a differentiated approach to the choice of the optimal method of hernioplasty and proper technique of surgery.

The aim is to develop an algorithm of hernioplasty method selection in patients with inguinal hernias based on the analysis of pathological changes resulting from hernia formation and peculiarities of the anatomical structure of the inguinal canal.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center, 306 patients with inguinal hernias of the abdomen aged from 16 to 82 years, 260 men (85%) were operated on in the period from 2016 to 2022. Primary inguinal hernias were diagnosed in 260 (85 %), recurrent - 46 (15 %), of which right-sided inguinal hernias were observed in 167 (54.6 %), left-sided - in 139 (45.4 %). Having analyzed the pathological changes of the inguinal canal that occurred during hernia formation, we came to the conclusion that none of the modern classifications fully reflects them. Nevertheless, the most acceptable is the classification of inguinal hernias according to Gilbert-Rutkowy. According to this classification and taking into account the height of the inguinal space and the degree of atrophy changes in the muscular-aponeurotic structures of the inguinal canal, we developed the following algorithm for choosing the method of hernioplasty.

Thus, in case of type I hernias (oblique hernia with non-expanded deep inguinal ring); II type (oblique hernia with dilated deep inguinal ring up to 2 cm and preserved posterior wall of the inguinal canal) with low inguinal space (1-2 cm), transabdominal pre-peritoneal laparoscopic hernioplasty (TAPP) is indicated, or autoplasty of the inguinal canal with mandatory narrowing of the deep inguinal ring by suturing the edges of the transverse fascia, methods: Marse+Martynov in women, Marse+Girard-Kimbarovsky or Bassini, Scholdais in men.

In hernias of type III (oblique hernia with dilated deep inguinal ring, more than 2 cm; type IV (direct hernia); type V (direct hernia with a small defect of the posterior wall) with low inguinal space (2 cm), and absent atrophy of muscular-aponeurotic structures of the inguinal canal, autoplasty of the posterior wall of the inguinal canal is indicated, methods: Bassini, Scholdais, or TAPP, or alloplasty according to Lichtenstein, PHS if the patient wishes.

In case of type VI hernias (combination of oblique and straight hernias); type VIII (recurrent hernia) with a low inguinal space (1-2 cm), absent atrophy of muscular-aponeurotic structures of the inguinal canal, alloplasty of the posterior wall of the inguinal canal with anterior placement of the prosthesis is indicated, Lichtenstein or PHS methods.

In type VII hernias (femoral hernia) with low vascular lacuna (up to 2 cm), Bassini autoplasty is indicated, and with high (2-4 cm) - preperitoneal allogernioplasty according to Reeves or preperitoneal methods of allogernioplasty of inguinal and femoral hernias [5].

Alloplasty of the posterior wall of the inguinal canal with posterior placement of the prosthesis - the pre-peritoneal method of allogernioplasty - PSAGP is indicated for hernias of types III, IV, V, VI, VIII with a high inguinal space (3-5 cm) and in the presence of atrophic changes in the muscular-aponeurotic structures of the inguinal canal.

Prolene meshes and PHS system (Ethicon) were used for alloplasty.

The surgical intervention was performed under general or spinal anesthesia. In the postoperative period special attention was paid to the prevention of complications from the wound side, because their development especially in case of recurrent hernias increased with each subsequent operation due to the progression of morphofunctional insufficiency of tissues and foci of chronic infection on the "old" ligatures. For this purpose, along with wound drainage, antibiotic prophylaxis was prescribed before and during surgery and in the postoperative period.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the clinic 306 patients with inguinal hernias were operated on using the proposed algorithm of hernioplasty method selection.

Complications of inflammatory character were mainly observed among patients with concomitant obesity and diabetes mellitus and operated on for recurrent hernia. Infiltrate and serous inflammation in the area of the postoperative wound occurred in 6 (2.1%) patients. Moderate testicular edema was observed in 4 (1,2%) patients. These complications were eliminated by appropriate conservative measures. No suppuration of the postoperative wound was observed.

The long-term results of surgical treatment of inguinal hernias were studied at repeated examinations and questionnaires of the patients within 1 to 5 years. Hernia recurrences occurred in 2 (0,65 %) patients, including one as a result of postoperative wound suppuration. In the other after autoplasty as a result of early excessive physical activity and antisocial lifestyle. One year later, the patients with recurrences were successfully reoperated, they underwent alloplasty with prolene mesh. Thus, satisfactory and good results of surgical treatment of abdominal wall hernias with the use of polypropylene mesh were obtained in 99,35% of patients, which testifies to the high efficiency of the proposed algorithm of the choice of the operation method and the expediency of the wide use of auxiliary plastic materials.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Improvement of the results of surgical treatment of patients with inguinal hernias can be achieved by individual choice of the hernioplasty method taking into account pathological changes in the posterior wall of the inguinal canal and the height of the inguinal interval, technically correct performance of the operation itself, and due to the use of modern mesh implants.
2. The proposed algorithm of the operation method selection allows to minimize significantly the number of recurrences of inguinal hernias.
3. Modern classifications of inguinal hernias do not provide complete information about pathological changes in the inguinal canal during hernia formation and therefore, need to be supplemented.

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